

QUALITY OF LIFE MODEL FOR WELLBEING IN ELDERLY PERSON IN RANONG, THAILAND

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Abstract

There are several elements that cause a better quality of life however, financial security, health, job satisfaction, safety, and family life are the major elements that increase the quality of life of people. Quality of life of a person, with the passage of time, demands a change in priorities of the major elements that increase the quality of life of people. Hence, quality of life in elderly persons requires certain attention for their social, financial, and health satisfaction. A survey was conducted aiming to collect primary data for the achievement of the results of the present study. Hence, 340 elderly persons without gender discrimination were the respondents of the present study. Received primary data from the respondents were analyzed by using Partial Least Square (PLS) to obtain results. It is concluded that support from government policies and local organizations, plays a significant role in making the better physical health of elderly persons and their quality of life. Because the physical health of an elderly person has a direct relationship with the quality of life of the person. The present study helps concerned authorities in government and local organizations to make their policies that can bring desirable outcomes particularly regarding the quality of life of elderly persons in Ranong, Thailand.

Keywords: Wellbeing, local organizations, physical health, quality of life, elderly person

1. Introduction

There is no big difference between the major component of the quality of life of an adult and an old. However, major components for a good life quality for an elderly person are; financial resources, mental health, satisfaction, social activity etc. It is determined that the majority of elderly persons are unable to enjoy a quality of life, especially in Ranong, Thailand (Wongsala, Anbäcken, & Rosendahl, 2021). Several factors have a significant influence on the quality of life of an elderly person in Ranong, Thailand, such as government policies and support from local organizations (Swasthaisong, 2019).

Quality of life of an elderly person has significant importance for his/her social development (Hinek, Stanić, & Škarica, 2019). Without proper social development, it is quite difficult for an elderly person to obtain or maintain subjective mental as well as physical health (Popovic & Masanovic, 2019). Like other members, an elderly person is also an influential member of a family. Hence, quality of life is essential for all the members of a family. The current study is

aimed to determine the role of government policies and support from the local organizations in the quality of life of an elderly person in Ranong, Thailand.

Several studies are available that describes the significance of quality of life of an elderly person, however, the current study is a unique study that determines the role of government policies and support from local organizations that have significant importance while making a good quality of life of elderly persons especially in Ranong of Thailand. Moreover, for a prosperous life of a family, good quality of life for all the members is mandatory, hence, in this context particularly, the current study plays an essential role. The current study helps to bring quality in spiritual, social, and psychological factors of life of an elderly person.

Several studies are available on the quality of life of an elderly person, however, there are only a few previous studies exploring the quality of life of an elderly person in Thailand (Whangmahaporn, 2019). It is determined that these previous studies have missed the role of government policies and support for local organizations for the quality of life of elderly persons in Ranong, Thailand. Hence, the current study is a unique study that determines the role of government policies and support from local organizations for the quality of life of elderly persons, especially in Ranong, Thailand.

The theoretical perspective of the current study describes the reality of the key variables such as government policies, support of local organizations physical health of an elderly person, and quality of life of an elderly person. Hence assumption about the reality of the relationship between the variables of the current study determines that; government policies and support of local organizations have a direct relationship with the physical health of an elderly person and the quality of life of an elderly person. However, the physical health of an elderly person mediates the relationship between independent variables (government policies and support of local organizations) and dependent variables (quality of life of an elderly person) of the current study.

2. Literature Review

However, it is mandatory for a person to maintain or gain maximum value for the attributes of a good quality of life. Several factors, directly and indirectly, have an influence on the attributes of a good quality of life however, according to the current study, government policies and support of local organizations play a vital role in the achievement of good quality of life of an elderly person. Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the current study.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the current study.

2.1 Government Policies and Physical Health of Elderly Person

Government policies have an essential role in the physical health of people. Government priorities while making policies and decisions based on gender and age group as per the need and requirements of the people. Both the central and local governments have a significant role in the physical health of people(Reeve, Thow, Baker, Hresc, & May, 2020). According to a previous study, unfortunately, people remain unable to enjoy a better version of their physical health particularly in the areas where poor policies are implemented by the government that doesn't facilitate the people instead cause worries for the people(Crouch, Radcliff, Strompolis, & Srivastav, 2019). It is also evident that implantation of declared policies by a government required more attention of the government, as most of the time, improper implementation of a good policy, unfortunately, makes the policy ineffective hence, such policies waste both the time and money and more importantly affected people and they have to face consequences for years because of the failure of a policy or its improper implementation by the government. However, according to the current study, government policies have an indispensable role in the physical health of elderly people of Ranong, Thailand. Hence, it is encapsulated that;

H1: Government Policies have a positive impact on the physical health of an elderly person.

2.2 Government Policies and Quality of Life of Elderly Person

The government collects initial data, information, and other necessary facts about the substance, subject, and problem of people, particularly under governance. As per the volume of allocated resources for a specific reason, the government makes policies aiming to deal with the problem of the people for that particular reason. Hence, maintaining a good quality of life for an elderly person is one of the basic issues for a government. Therefore, policies developed by a government play a significant role in the life of the people (Schepens, Van Puyenbroeck, & Maes, 2019). A better policy with a proper implementation that penetrates up to the root level of societies and has a significant role in reviving people's worries and problems, always helps both the government to govern people, and people to live a good quality of life. According to the present study, better policies by local as well as the central government in Ranong,

Thailand help elderly persons to live a good quality of life. However, weak policies by the government silently perplex people, and they remain unable to live a good quality of life. Hence, it is encapsulated that

H2: Government policies have a positive impact on the quality of life of an elderly person.

2.3 Support of Local Organizations and Physical Health of Elderly Person

Governments in developing countries don't have the required volume of resources, hence, these governments use to prioritize their limited resource to overcome general issues of people under their governance. In such scenarios, the role of local government and stakeholders becomes very influential and has a significant impact on the lives of the people. A prior study shows that in developing countries, support from local organizations has a vital role in the lives of people by offering them various kinds of facilities such as life insurance, educational loans, and other financial aids (Teles, Napolskij, Paúl, Ferreira, & Seeher, 2021). At present in developing countries such as Thailand, it is quite impossible to implement government policies at the root level where every individual can equally be benefited from the government policies. Hence, support from the local organization is essential. According to the present study, it is determined that the physical health of elderly persons is more stable than the elderly persons who are not in the network of support of local organizations. Hence, it is encapsulated that;

H3: Support of local organizations has a positive impact on the physical health of an elderly person.

2.4 Support of Local Organizations and Quality of Life of Elderly Person

Quality of life of elderly persons is wellness in result of combination of emotional, physical, and social factors. Hence, health of emotional, physical, and social factors determines the quality of elderly persons. It is evident that elderly persons need more care and attention to obtain or maintain a good quality of life (Su & Wang, 2019). Although governments and responsible authorities as well as responsible persons at domestic level, allocate enough budget to achieve a good quality of life of an elderly person. However, the role of support from local organizations cannot be neglected. As support of local organizations directly enables elderly persons to achieve a good quality of life. Hence, elderly persons with support of local organizations enjoy a good quality of life as compared to the elderly persons who are not the part of network of support of local organizations. Support from local organizations help elderly persons to overcome their common issues such as poor health, educational, cultural, and economic issues. Hence, it is encapsulated that;

H4: Support of local organizations has a positive impact on the quality of life of an elderly person.

2.5 Physical Health of Elderly Person and Quality of Life of Elderly Person

Quality of life of an elderly person depends upon person's social, physical health, and economic values. However, many other factors such as an elderly person's relationship with other family members and society, psychological factors, and the person's approach to deal with other people (de Oliveira, Souza, Rodrigues, Fett, & Piva, 2019). It is also evident that

environmental changes also have a direct relationship with the quality of life an elderly person. According to the current study value of physical health is one of the major factors that has numerous impacts on the quality of life of an elderly person. Increased value of physical health of an elderly person helps the person to maintain a good quality of life even with limited resources. A healthier life of an elderly person boosts the person's physical stamina that helps him/her to go for necessary physical exercises, workplaces, and social gathering that again add values for a good quality of life of the elderly person. While an elderly person with a weak physical health must depends on others and this limit the elderly person to enjoy a good quality of life. Hence, it is encapsulated that;

H5: Physical health of an elderly person has a positive impact on the quality of life of the elderly person.

H6: Physical Health of Elderly Person mediates the relationship between government policies and the quality of life of an elderly person.

H7: Physical health of an elderly person mediates the relationship between support of local organizations and the quality of life of an elderly person.

3. Research Methodology

Quantitative research method was adopted for the present study. Qualitative and mixed method were not preferred because these both methods are not according to the nature of the present study. However, before the conduction of the survey, participants were selected. 340 elderly persons were selected as participant of the survey. However, a questionnaire was prepared before the conduction of the survey. In the questionnaire there were 3 major sections, each section comprises of questions about specific topics and subjects. First section of the questionnaire was containing the questions asked about the demographic information of the respondents. While the second section of the questionnaire contained questions related with the key variables of the present study such as government policies, support from local organizations, physical health of an elderly person, and quality of life of an elderly person. While the last section of the questionnaire contained 20 questions based on 5-point Likert Scale starting from 1 as "Strongly Agree" to 5 as "Strongly Disagree". After development of the questionnaire, area cluster sampling approach was preferred for the present study. After selecting area cluster sampling approach, sample size of the present study was decided as 340 as per the suggestions of Taasoobshirazi, G., & Wang, S. (2016). Hence, initially 340 elderly persons without gender discrimination, from various clusters in the Ranong of Thailand, were selected and their basic contact information such as postal and email address, contact number, name, age, and gender was gathered from their corresponding daycare centers, societies offices and responsible house holding members. Then copies of the questionnaire along with the brief description about the present study, were individually sent to the email address of each respondent. Moreover, each respondent was contacted via their provided phone number to provide them brief description about the questionnaire and the purpose of the current study.

4. Data Analysis

Smart PLS is one of the most important technique it is widely used by the previous studies and one of the most popular technique to analyze the primary data. Especially it is most recommended to check the relationship between variables for questionnaire survey. Therefore, the present study used PLS. especially, it is most recommended to check the relationship between variables for the help of questionnaire survey. Therefore, the present study uses PLS structural equation modeling for the present study. PLS SEM is based on two major steps. The first step is measurement model assessment and second step is structural model assessment. In measurement model assessment, the present study examines the factor loading, composite liability, convergent validity, discriminant validity, and average variance extracted (AVE).Figure 2 shows the measurement model assessment. Table 1 shows the factor loading. Factor loading must be above 0.5 to retain the items, the scale item having factor loading below 0.5, must be deleted. However, in the present study all the scale items have factor loading above 0.5.

Figure 2: Measurement Model

Table 1: Factor Loadings (n=340)

	Government Policies	Physical Health of Elderly Person	Quality of Life of Elderly Person	Support of Local Organizations
GP1	0.803			
GP2	0.772			
GP3	0.884			
GP4	0.848			
GP5	0.788			
PHEP1		0.761		
PHEP2		0.736		
PHEP3		0.809		
QLEP1			0.725	
QLEP2			0.836	
QLEP3			0.864	
QLEP4			0.629	
QLEP5			0.8	
SLO1				0.845
SLO2				0.703
SLO3				0.731
SLO4				0.843

Furthermore, Table 2 show the composite reliability (CR) and AVE. AVE must be above 0.5 and the present study achieved the criteria as shown in Table 2. Composite reliability is also above 0.7. Finally, discriminant validity achieved through HTMT which is given in Table 3.

Table 2: Reliability and Convergent Validity (n=340)

	Alpha	rho_A	CR	(AVE)
Government Policies	0.878	0.879	0.911	0.673
Physical Health of Elderly Person	0.757	0.763	0.813	0.592
Quality of Life of Elderly Person	0.831	0.845	0.882	0.601
Support of Local Organizations	0.793	0.827	0.863	0.613

Table 3: HTMT

	Government Policies	Physical Health of Elderly Person	Quality of Life of Elderly Person	Support of Local Organizations
Government Policies	0.82			
Physical Health of Elderly Person	0.694	0.769		
Quality of Life of Elderly Person	0.638	0.763	0.775	
Support of Local Organizations	0.824	0.71	0.71	0.783

Structural model is used for hypotheses testing. Results are given in Table 4. All the direct hypotheses are supported as t-value for all the hypotheses is higher than 1.64 with positive beta value. Furthermore, indirect effect is given in Table 5. Two indirect effect are examined. Both the indirect effect is supported.

Figure 3: Structural Model

Table 4: Direct Effect Results (n=340)

	(O)	(M)	SD	T Statistics	P Values
Government Policies -> Physical Health of Elderly Person	0.341	0.334	0.093	3.648	0
Government Policies -> Quality of Life of Elderly Person	0.012	0.004	0.006	1.999	0.021
Physical Health of Elderly Person -> Quality of Life of Elderly Person	0.526	0.517	0.117	4.489	0
Support of Local Organizations -> Physical Health of Elderly Person	0.43	0.438	0.087	4.962	0
Support of Local Organizations -> Quality of Life of Elderly Person	0.346	0.35	0.102	3.38	0.001

Table 5: Indirect Effect Results

	(O)	(M)	SD	T Statistics	P Values
Government Policies -> Physical Health of Elderly Person -> Quality of Life of Elderly Person	0.179	0.176	0.073	2.465	0.014
Support of Local Organizations -> Physical Health of Elderly Person -> Quality of Life of Elderly Person	0.226	0.221	0.048	4.657	0

5. Discussion

The first hypothesis of the present study demonstrates that government policies have a positive impact on the physical health of an elderly person. Previous literature shows that government policies that are properly developed and appropriately implemented, cause happiness, balanced physical health, and social integrity of people under the governance (Fullagar, 2019). Hence, the physical health of people especially elderly person is directly influenced by the policies of their government.

The second hypothesis of the present study demonstrates that government policies have a positive impact on the quality of life of an elderly person. The quality of life of people is not as strong mostly in the countries that cannot develop influential policies due to their limited resources, particularly regarding health issues of the people under governance (Luque-Suarez, Martinez-Calderon, & Falla, 2019). The quality of life of people is good in developed countries as compared to the developing countries (Kvasničková Stanislavská, Pilař, Margarisová, & Kvasnička, 2020).

The third hypothesis of the present study demonstrates that support of local organizations has a positive impact on the physical health of an elderly person. The financial condition of a person directly influences the physical health of the person (Cappetto & Tadros, 2021). Availability of excessive money helps to maintain physical health (Subramaniam et al., 2019). However, achieving or maintaining physical health becomes difficult for a person who doesn't have financial support. Hence, organizations that financially support people, become fulgent

The fourth hypothesis of the present study demonstrates that support of local organizations has a positive impact on the quality of life of an elderly person. Previous literature shows that support of local organization is considered as an influential pillar of economic system of a region (Bezdenezhnykh, Bezdenezhnykh, & Karanina, 2020). Financial, social and cultural support from local organizations helps people especially elderly persons to achieve their desire level of life (Zhong, Wang, & Nicholas, 2020). Without support from local organizations, elderly person mostly remains unable to maintain or gain a good quality of life with their limited resources.

The fifth hypothesis of the present study demonstrates that physical health of an elderly person has a positive impact on the quality of life of the elderly person. Studies available on physical health shows that a good physical health is essential for achieving a good mental health while

a good mental health is also mandatory to acquire a good physical health (Lundström, Jormfeldt, Hedman Ahlström, & Skärsäter, 2020). While both the good physical and mental healths are essential for a good quality of life.

Last two hypotheses of the present study demonstrates that physical health of elderly person mediates the relationship between government policies and the quality of life of an elderly person. And physical health of an elderly person mediates the relationship between support of local organizations and the quality of life of an elderly person.

6. Conclusion

Age is a factor that decreases quality of life. Decrease in quality of life is common at the last part of the age of a person. However, there are several reasons that cause for decrease in the quality of life. According to the present study, role of government policies and support from local organizations is very influential on quality of life especially an elderly person. Results from analyzed data of the present study show that effective government policies and their proper implementation help elderly persons especially in Ranong of Thailand to maintain or gain a good quality of life. Resultant data also demonstrates that, government policies such as empowerment and social justice system provide privilege to their senior citizens from income tax, medical expenditures, extra interest, security, and travel. Moreover, government build and maintain day care centers, medical vans, and emergency units to look after elderly persons. As per the results of the present study support from local organizations is one of the major contributors in the maintaining the good quality of life of elderly persons in Ranong, Thailand.

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